

URBANIZATIONS AND THEIR IMPLICATIONS

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Introduction

India as a developing country is urbanizing at a rapid pace. Though the current level of urbanization in India is lowest as compared to the other developing countries. The absolute size of urban population is enormous. By the turn of the millennium about 300 million Indians lived in nearly 3700 towns and cities (urban areas) spread across the length and breadth of the country. This comprised of nearly 30 per cent of its total population in sharp contrast to 60 million (15 per cent) who lived in urban areas in 1947 at the time of our independence. During the last 50 years the population has grown two and a half times more and the urban India has grown as almost second largest in the world, only next to China. 21st century is set to become India's urban century with more people living in cities and towns than in the country side (rural areas) (Goldman Sachs, 2007). India has 10 of the fastest growing cities in the world and is witnessing massive urbanization. This research paper aims at analyzing the growth of urbanization in India, and its environmental and economic effects. For the analysis purpose the data from 1901, 1991, 2001 and 2011 census is used.

Pattern, trend and growth of urbanization in India:

Urbanization is the process by which large numbers of people become permanently concentrated in relatively small areas, forming cities. Internal rural to urban migration means that people move from rural areas to urban areas. The growth, trend and pattern of urbanisation since 1901 to 2011 has been shown as follows

Table No.1 Pattern, trend and growth Urbanisation in India since 1901 to 2011

Census Years	Number of Towns	Urban population (In Millions)	Per cent Urban to total population	Annual growth rate	Rate of urbanisation
1901	1916	25.9	10.8	-	-
1911	1908	25.9	10.3	0.0	-0.46
1921	2048	28.1	11.2	0.8	0.87
1931	2220	33.5	12.0	1.7	0.71
1941	2422	44.2	13.8	2.8	1.50
1951	3060	62.4	17.3	3.5	2.54
1961	2700	78.9	18.0	2.3	0.40
1971	3126	109.1	19.9	3.2	1.06
1981	4029	159.5	23.3	3.8	1.72
1991	4689	217.6	25.7	3.1	1.02
2001	5161	284.5	27.8	2.7	0.82
2011	7935	377	31.15	2.93	1.21

Source: <http://www.censusindia.gov.in>

Decadal growth of towns in India since 1901 to 2011

Trend in urbanisation from 1901 to 2011 are explained in the number of urban agglomeration have more than trebled and have increased from 1827 in 1901 to 7935 in 2011.

There was steady increase in number of towns till 1951, but due to more rigorous test applied in 1961 to determine whether a place qualified to be treated as a town or not many urban places were classified and hence, the number of towns declined from 3060 in 1951 to 2700 in 1961. There has been around 3.5 times growth in urban population in last four decades which increased from 109 million in 1971 to 377 million in 2011.

Implications of Urbanisation:

Implication of urbanisation as follows.

I) Urbanisation and Economic Development:

Economic development and urbanisation are often positively linked. Cities are the driving force for economic development. Economic growth also stimulates urbanisation. Neo-classical economists view urban centres as the engines of growth for the region or the country. Concentration of population and economic activity in space has been considered crucial for leveraging certain external economies that provide a base for improvement in efficiency, technological innovation and access to global market. The fact that growth impulse originates from the cities and towns is supposedly confirmed by the fact that per capita urban income is generally higher than that in rural areas.

Urban centres in India are characterized by extreme heterogeneity in terms of their socio-economic characteristics. Large cities exhibit distinctly lower poverty ratios. There was a decline in urban poverty from 49.01% in 1973-74 to 32.36% in 1993-1994. During the same period rural poverty declined from 56.44% to 37.27%. These cities also provide better social and physical infrastructure, including educational facilities, which results in higher productivity (Sviekauskas 1975).

The urbanisation trends in India are a direct reflection of the structural changes that are taking place in the economy. The combined contribution of industry and services to GDP is significantly higher than that of agriculture. The urban areas are likely to play an increasingly important role with the continuing liberalisation of the economy. Much of the growth of the economy will come from economic activities that are likely to be concentrated in and around existing cities and towns, particularly large cities. Cities with transport and telecom linkages with global economy, are the preferred destinations for investments. However, there is inadequate recognition of the role that cities play in economic development. The cities need to be supported with improved planning and infrastructure to accommodate growth, better governance and management.

The contribution of the urban sector to the Indian economy rose to 47% in 1980-81 as against 20% in 1950-51. By the end of 2001, it is 60%. This relation between urban areas and secondary and tertiary economic activities is contributing to the rapid increase in urbanisation in the country.

The growth of employment in urban areas has been higher than overall employment average in the country. Growth rate of employment during 1977-78 to 1987-88 averaged at about 4% per annum while the growth rate of employment in the rural areas was less than 1% per annum.

While there has been an overall rise in income in the urban areas there is considerable disparity between the different groups. The income distribution is considerably skewed as in the case of large cities in the country. Projections indicate that the percentage of households below the poverty line in Mumbai Metropolitan Areas will fall from 25% in 1991 to nearly zero in Mumbai city, and less than 5% in the Mumbai Metropolitan Region by 2011.

II) **Urbanisation and Environment:**

Managing the urban environment is emerging as an important issue and has become major subject of concern. Currently awareness of environmental urban problems continues to centre around air and water pollution. The process of rapid urbanisation poses serious challenge to towns and cities, which are struggling to provide and maintain the already inadequate level of urban services.

The urban heat island has become a growing concern and is increasing over the years. The urban heat island is formed when industrial and urban areas are developed and heat becomes more abundant. In rural areas, a large part of the incoming solar energy is used to evaporate water from vegetation and soil. In cities, where less vegetation and exposed soil exists, the majority of the sun's energy is absorbed by urban structures and asphalt. Hence, during warm daylight hours, less evaporative cooling in cities allows surface temperatures to rise higher than in rural areas.

Additional city heat is given off by vehicles and factories, as well as by industrial and domestic heating and cooling units. This effect causes the city to become 2 to 10° F (1 to 6° C) warmer than surrounding landscapes. Impacts also include reducing soil moisture and intensification of carbon dioxide emissions. Global warming, air pollution, water scarcity and pollution and loss of forest cover, agricultural land and depletion of wildlife as a result of urban sprawl, pose serious threats to the environment.

Urban areas suffer from serious problems of environmental pollution. There are high levels of air pollution and noise pollution due to industries and automobiles. Water is also polluted due to industrial wastewater discharge. Solid waste generation in urban areas is very high, and its proper disposal is a major problem.

Proper sewerage facilities are often lacking in urban areas. In the crowded slums, the human waste is just deposited in gutters or vacant spaces, which become a breeding ground for pathogenic bacteria spreading salmonella and hepatitis infections. In most of the cities heavy rainfall totally upsets the sewerage system. Cities are warmer than villages. Due to lot of heat released by various types of human activities in cities, which get retained by built structures and then slowly released into the atmosphere there is creation of urban heat island. This problem can be partially tackled by growing green belts of trees.

III) Measures:

Urbanization also provides several benefits when there is a well-planned city with proper transportation and residential facilities, reducing pollution problems.

Cities today need the tools to tackle unprecedented environmental and economic challenges. They share a set of challenges related to climate change, globalization and sustainability. They have to challenge of maintaining and rising living standards for growing population. For this Indian cities must have:

Renewable Energies: Electricity networks are able to take into account behavior of all the connected users in order to efficiently deliver sustainable, economic and secure electricity supplies.

People Mobility with info: Innovative and sustainable ways to provide transport of people in cities.

Pollution Control: Controlling emission and effluent by using different kinds of devices.

Public space management: care maintenance and active management of public space to improve the attractiveness of cities. Solutions to be provided information about the main places.

Digital Education: Extensive use of modern ICT tools in public schools.

Lastly the research paper will suggest for Indian Urbanization to develop plan cities.

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